

MESS 0020

GEO 2.21 - Andy Hall's "Crooked Smile" keystone (CSK) hypothesis¹ FOUND; the Pine Mountain Flux and the improbability of uplift².

Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM
October 2022

Keywords: Pine Mountain - Crooked Smile Keystone - A. Hall - Cumberland Gap - Big South Fork

¹ [Andrew Hall: The Keystone Pattern | Thunderbolts](#)

² With ancillary commentary on the Middlesboro Crater: astrobleme or electro-bolide?; and other anomalies

ABSTRACT

Figure 1 contains in-situ proof of the Yelverton³ lab found A- evidence, upon which A. Hall based his “crooked smile” keystone in his particularly salient electrogeological framework. The author’s work has been primarily in fieldwork⁴, while most contemporaries have been satisfied with macrolytic or microscopic examination and simple empiricism (Steinbacher). Other than Hall’s work, most of it lacks A++ evidence. This research, building upon MESS0018⁵ presents overlapping A++ evidence as to Yelverton’s (visual) identification and Hall’s sonics in “Arc Blasted Earth.”⁶

Aside from identifying the CSK in the Pine Mountain Flux, this work provides key evidence as to the expected formation or differentiation in cosmological geologic formation (antediluvian, perhaps pre-Pleistocene) for the anode, cathode, and the magnetic and gravitic anomalies. Keep in mind the author’s find is based on Hall’s diagram⁷ (figure 2, 2022), although the thought process pre-dated Andy’s CSK release (see: Figure 3).

Nevertheless, several mysteries remain, such as the issue of the bow-shock at Middlesboro Crater indicating a bolide collision⁸, and the Wildcat Mountain flux energy gradient which causes so many car accidents in Kentucky’s I-75 “grapevine”⁹. Nevertheless, the Crater as an electro-bolide has support from P.M. Jupp’s work on the 1491 Melbourne electro-comet¹⁰ dual strike and electrical explosion (with instant petrification on beach, in situ). However Hall’s assertion is a direct arc EDM -

perhaps counter-rotational Birkeland Current) over the area in another Hallian super-vortex¹¹. This strains the author’s credulity as to the causation of the bow shock. This issue resurges at the Hicks Dome boundary¹² where A++ electrogeological evidence found by the author¹³ correlates with a Juppian electro-bolide. This inability of the author to resolve this issue reduces the AIM grade from A+ to A. However the evidence grade for the

³ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology/yelverton>

⁴ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/electrogeology>

⁵ [MESS0018: GEO 2.2 - Magnetic Anomalies in VA and KY](#)

⁶ [Andrew Hall: The Arc-Blasted Earth | EU2016](#)

⁷ Figure 2 - “Andy Hall: The Keystone Pattern” - the Yelverton-Hall CSK hypothesis; credit: A. Hall/Thunderbolts Project©

⁸ https://www.academia.edu/69494986/Plasmaglyphs_Introduction pp. 19, Figure 6

⁹ Coloration may help in this and meteorological analysis, but the indescribable quality of driving the grapevine is indirectly correlated with optical (color) data. Rather than attraction, most people prefer to drive faster through the area, missing key lake and historical opportunities. See: www.hiddendestinationsky.com

¹⁰ “Melbourne 1491” <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology/jupp>

¹¹ [Andrew Hall: Ionic Winds Shaped Earth | Space News](#) etc. (3 parts)

¹² Where Earthquakes cluster.

¹³ https://www.academia.edu/49456803/Trip_Report_Pebble_Beach_Red_River_Gorge

entire Kithiki/"Red Bird" CSK remains rated A++ due to multiple macrolytic, macroscopic, and in the future: microscopic data.

Hidden Kithiki

Long before this video was released, the author recognized this formation as unusual and straining all upthrust theories. Not just from his Megafauna work but pre-EPEMC in his Hidden Kentucky Work:

Figure 3 - The Jellico Bend - a 90-degree formation in Pioneer, TN and clear evidence for the CSK; credit: Google Maps

www.hiddendestinationsky.com

Figure 4 - The Pine Mountain Flux in stepped EDM etching; is KY Ridge formed from arc-blasted winds? credit: google/author

In figure 4 you can just make out the bow shock, as well as the first terminus (first anode): the Pine Gap/Chained Rock, where the arc EDM “leaped” across to begin an even longer series of chains. Bear in mind that Hall’s CSK is not necessarily indicative of his overall hypothesis being fulfilled. Yelverton did **not** have a super vortex in his lab work, nor is there any proof that the Valles Marineris or the Richat Structure (which the author first provided work on previous to Hall) ever had super vortices that “hovered” over them, creating long term changes. This idea - an Earthen “White Spot” equivalent to Jupiter’s Red Spot - has plenty of hurdles to overcome to achieve the A++ evidence in Hall’s first presentation, the author’s Thunderbolt finding, this work, Jupp’s work, and the author’s trip reports.

However, the overall “on the nose” macrolytic effect necessitates a macroscopic and later in other papers a microscopic (mineral) investigation!

Macroscopic Analysis

Anode - the Breaks of VA/KY and “Devil’s Bend(s)”

Figure 5 - the Devil’s Bend at Breaks Interstate Park, VA: a direct look at the anode, and a common feature of highly energized parks like the Grand Canyon (a Lichtenberg formation); credit: B.Stack/WJHL¹⁴

Important note: the coloration (lighting) for photographs is highly photogenic at the Breaks, and other sites mentioned in this exposé.

Cathode - the draw of Precipitation

Looking at Figure 1 it is clear that there is something unusual about the pileup of atomic Mass-Energy (AME) at the location. If the upthrust comes from the southeast, then it should be mostly accumulated to the northwest, not the west. The idea that the thrust was directly horizontal into the “Jellico Bend” is really quite laughable and strains the credulity of any serious thinker. Therefore, if lab data of electrogeology provides better macrolytic evidence or data, and we find this in the macroscopic investigation, then we must, surely, choose the better explanation that involves stronger forces. Tectonic plates are nowhere near the VA/KY/TN junction, and assuredly have little to do with the issue!

Figure 6 - Magnetic Anomalies of KY/TN; credit: USGS¹⁵

¹⁴ <https://www.wjhl.com/community/trail-team-11/trail-notes-breaks-interstate-park/>

¹⁵ https://pubs.usgs.gov/sm/mag_map/mag_s.pdf

But what we also see is the combination of higher altitudes, and slopes, with increased rainfall. We also saw this in 0018's brief discussion of the energy flux density north of the Red River Gorge, along the Daniel Boone National Forest leyline, a distinctly differently - and perhaps older - formed flux, It has a different angle, and a different tendency. The author thinks they are both related to the Shamash era, but admits the Pine Mountain flux could be Jovian era.

It is difficult to separate the Black Mountains' high altitude from the precipitation increase. But what about the Cumberland Gap itself? This is a low, even absent, altitude, and yet there is a precipitation draw. Looking at Figure 6 we see the Anode has a magnetic escarpment, and this is probably also something found, in smaller scale, at the Middlesboro Crater. But, for now, according to the figure, the Gap has a magnetic accumulation (as compared to the Earth's average magnetic field).

Black Mountain - Raised Landmasses in a + Charge environment

Magnetic anomalies continue to accumulate along the anode-cathode axis, with a peak roughly halfway between.

Figure 7 - Black Mountain, KY; granite, limestone, and coal; credit: peakbagger.com

The Big Stone Gap

The author is unsure if this is the right "cross" terminus (using Ywahoo as the C end on the upper-left end), because it doesn't create a perfect cross through KY Ridge or Cumberland Gap. However, it is a very interesting geological feature and is a proposed terminus.

Figure 8 - Big Stone Gap, VA; credit: Imgur

Pine Mountain flux - Increasing Turbulence from Source

Looking at Figure 1 and 3, one can see that the EDM etching of Pine Mountain starts with very acute/sharp angles, and narrow ridges, and then they get wavier, and wider, as the formation¹⁶ moves away from the Source and Secondary (Cumberland Gap?).

The Jellico Bend

The most unique - and important - signatory feature of the CSK is the 90-degree bend. Here we see not just the ideal conditions in the Yelverton lab, but an actual 90 degree mountain chain bend. But instead of excavated material, the conditions were reversed, and as a result, mountains were created.

¹⁶ anode uplift - caused by a moving/retracting anode from the source-cathode towards the final location at the Breaks

Figure 9 - The Jellico Bend; credit: [topozone.com](https://www.topozone.com)¹⁷

Consider the bend as a form of Lorentz identification. We do not understand this science, because no one has done the microscopic work on Yelverton's macrolytic lab evidence enough to come up with a more precise scientific identification. But clearly, sinusoidal rise and fall is implicated.

The Kentucky Ridge

This area, also proximal to the Pine Mountain State Resort Park, is home to a wide variety of diverse species. This area has many of the same characteristics as the Smoky Mountains rainforest, but with less elevation to cause this much rainfall. Coincidence?

Figure 10 - "Pine Mountain Mists" (from the Lodge); credit: author

Blanton Forest

One of the unique regions is a large stand of Original Growth trees in the Blanton Forest SNP. There is also a 4-H/Boy Scout camp there. The hike is very lush, and similar in many respects to that of the Ywahoo. The jumble of stones is mostly like those found anywhere in sandstone-riddled Kentucky and DBNF leyline, but there is an extra quality of lushness and originality, matched only at Ywahoo, Lily Cornett Woods, and few other places.

The Red Bird Magnetic Limb

Figure 1 makes reference to the "sun" area of the CSK diagram, using a hexagon. Indeed there is something incredibly primeval about the Red Bird Region of the Daniel Boone National Forest. It is the only major section "off-line" but the US Government knew to preserve the region. It is incredibly lush, and mostly unexplored by the general public. Highly recommended, but beware the flash flooding which can occur in the Red Bird¹⁸ River basin.

¹⁷ <https://www.topozone.com/tennessee/campbell-tn/summit/jellico-mountain-2/>

¹⁸ Named both for the Cardinal and Chief Redbird. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Massacre_at_Ywahoo_Falls

Red Bird's Caves and Plasmaglyphs

These unique historical ideograms, petroglyphs, and cave/rock art are relatively unprotected priceless treasures, which the state, and State Archaeology (of the University of Kentucky and University of Louisville, etc.) have left, abandoned and exposed. Chief Red Bird was assassinated, along with his friend, and more importantly the Chilokee truths and history. One should consult the "Myths of the Cherokee"¹⁹ text for more information.²⁰

It is uncoincidental that these glyphs are in the region near to this magnetic limb.

Figure 11 - Red Bird's glyphs, kept inside his cave where he lived, and later died (nearby); credit: author

The Big South Fork Gravity Anomaly

Looking at the anomaly, the overriding interest of the author is in the a) amount of rainfall or sudden summer thunderstorms known in the area (With which he has personal testimonial to, and numerous photographic evidence) and b) the similarity in electrification evidence and energy flux as the Red River Gorge area. More to the point: the Yahoo Falls area, and the natural gas vents (of legend) and coal mines within the Devil's Jump area which provide more evidence of transmutation in cosmological events. Also, the numerous

¹⁹ <https://www.sacred-texts.com/nam/cher/motc/index.htm>

²⁰ Lies have been told and spread, and the growing and telling of them by the mainstream is a serious problem. Despite this, EPEMC makes progress in honoring their knowledge and traditions, and encourages more work of the same.

arches of McCreary County (over 500 arches and windows), provide some evidence of a unique event in the area. Probably not the same EDM formation event as the Pine Mountain CSK/flux event, but something similar. Perhaps it was the same star or planet that provided the arc, but on a larger and wider scale? The average width of the DBNF leyline is around 15 miles, while the Pine Mountain flux is rarely beyond 2 miles and usually 1.3-1.8 miles wide.

Figure 12 - Yahoo Falls; credit: wiki

The Ywahoo Falls & Arch - “People of the Cave” worship the Great/Squatter Lord

The Ywahoo/Yeh /Yao /Yahweh worldwide sound is the sound of atmospheric and/or land deformation caused by the buckling of the Spheres of Heaven & Earth²¹ by the electrostatic (Lorentz) force. This occurred in the pre-Megalithic, certainly, although it may also be that during the Jovian era the orbit around Jupiter (or was it still proto-Jupiter?) the sounds were re-heard, but as trumpets (even as they still are, worldwide). Nevertheless, the association of “The [Star] Lord [Storm God]” with the Great/Squatter Man was a worldwide phenomenon. See the Chinese plasmaglyphics series for more information.

The People of the Caves were probably - just like the post-Tepians and early or pre-Capadocians, the inhabitants of caves and dolmens.²² Perhaps as descendents of the Archaic Indians became the Cherokee, or perhaps they had a similar, continent wide tradition. It isn’t clear, but what is clear is that the Nation inhabited the Kithiki (up until the Padoucans/Allegewi²³ invasion, and then the spread of the Cahokian/Mississippians²⁴ - and the Chinese²⁵ pox), both of which affected the Cherokee starting in the 1100s and later the mid 1400s. The final remnants in the area experienced a massacre from the Shawnee and pioneers in a “nits make lice”²⁶ ethnic cleansing campaign, leaving Chief Red Bird as the last. The Ywahoo Falls appears to have been *where* the women and children took their desperate last refuge (in the Lord).

Yucatan-like Jungle “Qi” flux of a He-point

Beneath the Ywahoo (as it is properly said, and not “yay-who”) Falls is a region of “uniting” which the Chinese call He 合. It is a confluence of tributaries of water, and of energy, overlooked by the magnificent overhang of the 112 foot waterfall. This area is populated by a small number of giant “grandfather” stones²⁷, which show great antiquity, and the area feels much like a Central American jungle or Mayan area. It would have been considered sacred for this reason alone, even without signs of electrogeology or mythic thunderbolts and

²¹ HEGEME and the Plasma-Electromagnetic Sky

²² Discourses on an Alien Sky—Preface | The Meaning of Ancient Myths (playlist)

²³ Whom the Cherokee called the Nicotani

²⁴ Whom the Cherokee called the Ani'-kuta'nī <https://www.sacred-texts.com/nam/cher/motc/motc108.htm>

²⁵ <https://www.sacred-texts.com/nam/cher/motc/motc106.htm>

²⁶ <http://www.northerncherokeemission.com/children-massacre-at-ywahoo-falls.html>

²⁷ Figure 13 - Grandfather Stones of the Ywahoo; credit: author

thunderbirds. However, like the Great Serpent Mound, one cannot help but wonder if there is more than a mere correlation of events in this matter.

Figures 14-17: Cove Lake Park, inside the Jellico Bend, in Tennessee; credit: author

The quality of the lighting was *unusually* good, particularly considering the coincidental timing. The author cannot help but think the lighting was so special because of the relationship of the lake and park to the being nestled inside the mountain fold, and beneath its shadow. Enjoy.

Conclusion

The discovery of a provable, macro-sized Crooked Smile Keystone is almost as important in electrogeology as the finding of the Perattian Thunderbolt as the cryptoexplosive site of the Big Sink²⁸. However, it is certainly more mysterious, both in its tremendous scale of energy and formation, and the epoch of its genesis. Moreover, there are more factors to consider than in a simple magnetospheric-induced Perattian Thunderbolt of the Jovian era. Magnetics, electrogravitics, etching versus EDM-uplift, cathode and anode, and natural formations which affect wind, water, and biological behaviors all must be considered alongside mineral species and matrices.

Then, one must consider the electrometeorology and telluric currents, and as seen in MESS0019²⁹, the natural catastrophes affected by the interaction of the Plasma-electromagnetic Sky and the HEGEME. In effect, the Spheres of Heaven³⁰ and of Earth, which are shells of capacitance and induction, and storage and discharge surfaces of voltage and current.

This paper is a "lightning rod" cause for further exploration of the area, the epochs, and the electrogeological laboratory setups which can replicate these exact results, or what has been produced by Yelverton in his lab. It is also a catalyst for the encouragement of the audience to help Mr. Andy Hall find more of these types of formations *in situ*, to provide further supporting evidence not only of the CSK, but of electrogeology³¹ in general.

References

1. "The Keystone Pattern | Thunderbolts," Youtube/Thunderbolts Project, A. Hall, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HdfBGqWpW5w>
2. With ancillary commentary on the Middlesboro Crater: astrobleme or electro-bolide?; and other anomalies
3. "B. Yelverton," (EPEMC) Gateway/The Pulse, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology/yelverton>
4. "Electrogeology," (EPEMC) Gateway/ The Pulse, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/electrogeology>
5. "MESS0018: GEO 2.2 - Magnetic Anomalies in VA and KY," Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://docs.google.com/document/d/11VWfPxCudFLUAe8tjs4nEv-mSJ5yGS_UL0edWzqxKBA/edit
6. "The Arc-Blasted Earth | EU2016," Youtube/Thunderbolts Project, A. Hall, 2017, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fDIRMB3hVQM>
7. Figure 2 - "Andy Hall: The Keystone Pattern" - the Yelverton-Hall CSK hypothesis; credit: A. Hall/Thunderbolts Project©
8. "Plasma Petroglyphs (Plasmaglyphs), Earthworks, and the Megafauna Extinction," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2018, https://www.academia.edu/69494986/Plasmaglyphs_Introduction
9. "Hidden Destinations in Kentucky," The Map, Sf. R. Careaga, https://www.google.com/maps/d/viewer?mid=1hldTpY8nuJDiRws1PI5iLbLWJDM&hl=en_US&ll=38.01520770656196%2C-84.59047807023916&z=10

28

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332831733_Proposed_Discovery_of_Perattian_Thunderbolt_of_the_Gods_Strike_Location_in_Versailles_KY_Comparison_of_Predicted_Models_and_LiDAR_scans_of_Big_Sink_location_in_Woodford_County_Addendum_for_Plasmaglyph

29

https://www.academia.edu/88366336/MESS0019_Electrometeorology_2_1_The_2021_Mayfield_Kentucky_Tornado_Track_and_the_New_Madrid_gravity_and_magnetic_anomalies

³⁰ MESS0023: MET 2.22 - The Spheres of Heaven in the HEGEME

³¹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology>

10. "P. Mungo Jupp," (EPEMC) Gateway/The Pulse, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/researchers/electrogeology/jupp>
11. "Ionic Winds Shaped Earth | Space News- Three parts," Youtube/Thunderbolts Project, A. Hall, 2019, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=j5rRFkksvfc>
12. "Trip Report: Pebble Beach, Red River Gorge," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2021, https://www.academia.edu/49456803/Trip_Report_Pebble_Beach_Red_River_Gorge
13. "TRAIL TEAM 11 Trail Notes: Breaks Interstate Park," Nexstar Media/Channel 11 (Johnson City) B. Stack, 2019, <https://www.wjhl.com/community/trail-team-11/trail-notes-breaks-interstate-park/>
14. "Magnetic Anomaly Map of North America," https://pubs.usgs.gov/sm/mag_map/mag_s.pdf
15. "Jellico Mountain Topo Map in Campbell County TN," Topozone.com, <https://www.topozone.com/tennessee/campbell-tn/summit/jellico-mountain-2/>
16. "Massacre at Ywahoo Falls," Wikipedia, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Massacre_at_Ywahoo_Falls
17. "Myths of the Cherokee," Sacred Texts, J. Mooney, 2001, <https://www.sacred-texts.com/nam/cher/motc/index.htm>
18. "HEGEME and the Plasma-Electromagnetic Sky," Sf. R. Careaga, 2018, <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1UxHBiBCUcO6nB1jYI-Ar5O3QipgWb4LfcDcmHewyNLM/edit#heading=h.kyxfpc8zxwnu>
19. "Discourses on an Alien Sky—Preface | The Meaning of Ancient Myths," Youtube/Thunderbolts Project, D. Talbott, 2015, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AlfHeZQVEol&list=PLwOAYhBuU3UeFB-ygaH63Seg6r6C_dtqB
20. Whom the Cherokee called the Nicotan
21. Whom the Cherokee called the Ani'-kuta'ni: "The Massacre Of The Ani'-kuta'ni," Sacred Texts.com, <https://www.sacred-texts.com/nam/cher/motc/motc108.htm>
22. "The Giants From The West," Sacred Texts.com, <https://www.sacred-texts.com/nam/cher/motc/motc106.htm>
23. "Chickamauga Timeline The Great Cherokee Children Massacre at Ywahoo Falls" Northern Cherokee Nation.com, <http://www.northerncherokeemassacre.com/children-massacre-at-ywahoo-falls.html>
24. Figure 13 - Grandfather Stones of the Ywahoo; credit: author
25. "Proposed Discovery of Perattian Thunderbolt of the Gods Strike Location in Versailles, KY Comparison of Predicted Models and LiDAR scans of Big Sink location in Woodford County; Addendum for Plasmaglyphs and the Megafauna Extinction," Research Gate, Sf. R. Careaga, 2019, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332831733_Proposed_Discovery_of_Perattian_Thunderbolt_of_the_Gods_Strike_Location_in_Versailles_KY_Comparison_of_Predicted_Models_and_LiDAR_scans_of_Big_Sink_location_in_Woodford_County_Addendum_for_Plasmaglyphs
26. "MESS0019: Electrometeorology 2.1 -The 2021 Mayfield, Kentucky Tornado Track and the New Madrid gravity & magnetic anomalies," Academia, Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, https://www.academia.edu/88366336/MESS0019_Electrometeorology_2_1_The_2021_Mayfield_Kentucky_Tornado_Track_and_the_New_Madrid_gravity_and_magnetic_anomalies
27. "MESS0023: MET 2.22 - The Spheres of Heaven in the HEGEME," Sf. R. Careaga, 2022, <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1R-OIUtzjdRLf9C1OZNqjKdOBU3gl2ujDXh3tjJtR-ZM/edit>

